

**INSTITUTO MEXICANO DE ACUSTICA
ASOCIACION MEXICANA DE INGENIEROS Y TECNICOS EN RADIODIFUSION
(PUEBLA)
THE MEXICAN INSTITUTE OF ACOUSTICS
MEXICAN ASSOCIATION OF BROADCAST ENGINEERS AND TECHNICIANS (Puebla)**

**18 CONGRESO INTERNACIONAL MEXICANO DE ACÚSTICA (18th MEXICAN
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON ACOUSTICS)**

CHOLULA, PUEBLA, MEXICO

16 - 18 NOVIEMBRE, 2011 (November)

PL3 A Portable Chamber for Bat Field Recordings

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Abstract. Bats are plague controllers and effective pollinators for many plant species, and thus, an important link for the ecosystem balance. They have evolved a sophisticated system to analyse reflections from their own emitted sounds to perceive their environment; ability known as echolocation. These signals are therefore useful to classify and determine abundance and distribution of species. However, recording ultrasound is challenging since real time and frequency monitoring is not usually available. Moreover, ultrasound signals for echolocation are highly variable since they depend on environmental conditions, biotic factors, and the bat's task. Acoustic identification of species from their echolocation signals relies on having a reliable database of signals to compare. This paper describes a portable chamber that provides controlled and reproducible conditions for bat echolocation recordings. Conventional field recordings and recordings using the chamber for vespertilionid bats (*Lasiurus xanthinus* and *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus*) and Phyllostomid bats (*Leptonycteris yerbabuena*) are presented to highlight the advantages of using this chamber.

Resumen. Los murciélagos juegan un papel importante en el balance del ecosistema al ayudar al control de plagas y por su aportación como polinizadores. En el transcurso de la evolución han desarrollado un sistema sofisticado que les permite percibir su entorno mediante el análisis de las reflexiones de sus propios sonidos emitidos explícitamente para tal fin, facultad conocida como ecolocalización. Desde una perspectiva biológica, la clasificación de estas señales posibilita su uso para estudios de determinación de abundancia y distribución de especies. Sin embargo, la grabación de estas señales que caen en el intervalo ultrasónico impone ciertos retos dado que en general el monitoreo en tiempo real en los dominios de la frecuencia y el tiempo no es viable. Las señales ultrasónicas de ecolocalización por su parte, presentan un alto grado de variabilidad dado que dependen de factores ambientales, bióticos y la tarea específica que realice el murciélago. La identificación acústica de especies depende por tanto de contar con una base de datos confiable para comparación. Este trabajo propone el uso de una cámara de grabación portátil que proporcione condiciones controladas y reproducibles para la grabación de señales de ecolocalización. Con la finalidad de resaltar las ventajas en su uso se comparan grabaciones de murciélagos vespertilionidos (*Lasiurus xanthinus* y *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus*) y un filostómido (*Leptonycteris yerbabuena*) bajo condiciones convencionales y usando la cámara propuesta.

Keywords: bats, echolocation, portable chamber, recordings, database.

INTRODUCTION

Mammals such as bats use echolocation to perform navigation, detection, and classification of targets and often in highly cluttered environments. The signals exploited by bats have evolved over an immense period of time. Fossil bats found around 53 million years ago are thought to have possessed at least basic echolocation. Actually more than 800 bat species are known to use echolocation [1]. This wide variety of species habitat and geographic distribution suggest a grand variety of signals used for echolocation. In a single species an individual might change its echolocation calls depending on environmental conditions (vegetation structure, weather conditions, location, and habitat), biotic factors (presence of conspecifics, prey size, movement, defensive measures), and navigation strategy (seek and flee, pulse and evade, offset pursuit, wandering, exploring, arrival, obstacle and collision, containment, etc.) [1][2][3][4]. Call structure can also vary with gender and age [3].

Bats have the ability to catch flying insects while flying full speed in pitch darkness; their use of ultrasonic sound for navigation is astounding. Echolocation permits them to distinguish between a moth and a falling leaf. The calls are adaptation to specific habitat, supporting biology and ecology known [5][6]. In Mexico there are 137 species of bats grouped into eight families [7].

The extensive use that bats make of sound means it is possible to eavesdrop on these signals to detect their presence, assess their activity, and potentially, identify the species that emits the call [8][9][10]. Absolute abundance cannot be determined in most cases, but acoustic techniques combined with other survey techniques such as capturing, and roost counts, can be used to obtain the other two levels of survey, namely: presence or not detected and relative abundance [4].

Ultrasonic signals utilised by bats can be analysed looking for distinctive patterns of frequencies, pulse shapes, and rhythm/repetition. Figure 1, for example, shows a *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus* signal recorded in field using a time-expansion detector system (Pettersson D-240X) that converts the ultrasonic signal emitted by the bat to sonic frequencies by first digitalizing the signal and then playing it at a lower sample rate, in this case 10 times slower. The audio signal at the output of the time expansion system was recorded at a sampling rate of 96 kHz @ 24 bits using a Zoom digital recorder. Notice that in the time axis, due to the sampling rate change, what is labeled 1.0 seconds corresponds consequently to 1/10 of a second. Conversely, in the frequency axis, a label of 1 kHz corresponds to a real frequency of 10 kHz. Sections A, B, and C present the phases of location, detection, and the final feeding buzz. In the location phase A, bursts of 8 chirps per second (Pulse Repetition Rate) with sweeping frequencies from 55 kHz to 30 kHz in 11 milliseconds for the fundamental component (1) are shown, a PRR of 14 chirps with frequencies from 48 to 33 kHz in 7 ms (2) for detection, and a Pulse Repetition Rate of 160 chirps from 38 kHz to 20 kHz in 0.2 ms. in a feeding buzz. Figure 1 also highlights one of the main problems on field recordings; what seems to be a double pulse in B and C might be a second bat in the area. This might not be obvious on B, but becomes evident as an extra signal on the feeding buzz (3)

FIGURE 1 Spectrogram of echolocation signal recorded in field. Spectrogram setting: 1024 point FFT, Hamming window, 50% overlap.

Acoustic detection and identification, however, depends on counting with a reliable database of characteristic signals that could serve as model patterns for comparison. Although there are some databases available in the literature and on internet, the high variability of the signals due to environmental conditions, biotic factors, and navigation strategies, added to the specific recording conditions and variety of equipment, make comparisons among them difficult.

In this work, a portable chamber for field recording of echolocation signals is proposed as a mean of controlling some of these variables. The aim is to provide reproducible conditions for comparable field recordings. To the extent of the authors' knowledge there are no previous attempts in proposing a recording chamber for bat field recording.

In order to assess the performance of the chamber under real conditions, with specimens in their habitat, echolocation signals of Vespertilionidae and Phyllostomidae bats were recorded. Both families are widely distributed in Mexico. The former are insect eaters (smallest beetles, moths, mosquitoes, etc.) and most of them catch insects that inhabit water bodies. The latter are fruit eaters and important pollinators of cacti species [11].

DESIGN

Acoustic chambers have existed for a while used specially for musicians or for others physics studies; however, this is the first prototypes of portable chambers for bats recording.

A portable recording studio shall satisfy certain conditions for field studies. To be really portable, the camera should be easy to transport, have low weight, and be easy to deploy; and in order to encourage reproducibility, it should be preferably of low construction costs, using ready available materials. Once in the field the camera should be easy and fast to assemble; it shall provide enough acoustic isolation from conspecifics at ultrasound frequencies, and minimize inside reflections. The effects of wind noise and temperature changes ought to be minimized. The chamber must be capable of lodging the instruments and at least two persons, one for handling the instruments and another one to manipulate the organism or to allow the bat to fly.

In order to build the portable anechoic chamber, a frame of 1/2" PVC pipe was designed. It was used to support the acoustic material (orthopaedic foam pads). The pipes were joined together with 90° elbows and tee's forming poles and crossbars. Once the space needed for two persons, the instruments, and space for flight were determined, the measurements were dictated for the dimension of the acoustic material, i.e., the height of the chamber determined by the length of the foam pad, and its length and width was determined by the foam. On the edge of the chamber, the cushions were overlapped to avoid hollow. This way we obtained an almost cubic camera, each face area of 2 pads per side (Figure 2). Acoustic material was placed inside the frame, joining the foam pads between them with Velcro on the edges to form walls, roof, and floor. The walls were fixed to the frame using PVC tile edges as backup material, and nuts and bolts were drilled to the top crossbar. The sides of the roof rest on the frame and the centre was pulled up with a draw line fixed to the top frame of the brace. The floor foam pad just rested on the ground.

Parts List:

- 8 PVC pipes 1/2" of 180cm
- 8 PVC pipes 1/2" of 150 cm
- 4 PVC pipes 1/2" of 60 cm
- 4 PVC pipes 1/2" of 39 cm
- 4 PVC pipes 1/2" of 57 cm
- 30 PVC pipes 1/2" of 5 cm (aprox.) as joints
- 2 PVC tile edge 1/2" of 150 cm
- 2 PVC tile edge 1/2" of 180 cm
- 16 Plastic screws (and corresponding nuts)
- 14 Orthopaedic foam pads 1.80 m X 90cm
- 24 pieces of velcro (both sides) 90 cm
- 2 pieces of velcro (both sides) 130 cm
- 14 PVC 1/2" 90° elbows
- 34 PVC 1/2" Tees
- PVC glue / cement

FIGURE 2. Portable chamber assembled. Notice that orthopaedic foams are not placed yet and the zoom circle explains how to fit the PVC “T”s and elbows

ACOUSTIC TEST

One of the main problems during field recordings is the noise interference of insects and conspecific. Consequently, isolation at high frequencies is a highly desirable property of the chamber.

To evaluate the acoustic performance of the chamber, a Radox 80-1005N 75w piezoelectric tweeter, fed by a Wavetek Model 145 function generator, was used as a constant sound pressure force. Sinusoidal waveforms of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, and 80 kHz were fed to the tweeter, passing through the foam and received by a Pettersson D-240X time expansion bat detector (Figure 3). The sound output of the bat detector, now shifted to sonic range, was recorded using a Zoom Digital recorder sampling at 96 kHz and 24 bits. To find the absorption of the foam to different frequencies, the same procedure was repeated but without the foam. Recordings at each frequency (with and without foam) were analysed with Adobe Audition version 3.0 to obtain average power and calculate the differences. The results are shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 3. Experiment design, where A is the Zoom4n Recorder, B is the Pettersson D-240X Detector, C is the orthopaedic foam, D is a twitter and E is a Signal generator.

In Figure 4 the isolating effect of the foam is shown. For frequencies beyond 40 kHz the attenuation increases for 35 dB to up to 70 dB for 80 kHz. Since most echolocation signals from bats are found within this bandwidth, this chamber has the required isolation to avoid unwanted signals from conspecifics flying outside the chamber.

FIGURE 4. Acoustic isolation of the foam

FIELD METHODS

Parastrellus hesperus hesperus, *Lasiurus xanthinus*, and *Leptonycteris yerbabuena* individuals were captured in a mist net (Avinet, Inc., Dryden, New York). A net site where water features, topography, and vegetation provided the best opportunities to catch bats (set along wetland and xeric-riparian habitats) was selected.

The nets were monitored regularly for five hours. Species and sex of captured bats were determined by external inspection [12]. Bats were handled following the American Society of Mammalogists Animal Care and Use Guidelines [13].

Echolocation calls were recorded inside the chamber using a time-expansion detector system (Pettersson D-240X, Pettersson Elektronik AB, Uppsala, Sweden) at a sampling rate of 96 kHz at 24 bits using a Zoom4n digital recorder.

STUDY AREA

Bats were captured at “El Rosario” located 6.5 Km S El Triunfo, Baja California Sur ($23^{\circ}44'31.73''\text{N}$, $-110^{\circ}6'41.99''\text{W}$, Figure 5). Vegetation near the collection site is dominated by date palm tree (*Phoenix dactylifera*), tree tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*), palo blanco (*Lysiloma candidum*), cacti (*Pachocereus pringlei*), mesquite (*Prosopis palmeri*), cholla (*Cylindropuntia cholla*), palo verde (*Cercidium microphyllum*), matorra (*Jatropha cuneata*), and vinorama (*Acacia farnesiana*).

The area is semiarid with warm weather; the region has an annual mean temperature between 22°C and 24°C , and the climate type, according to Köppen’s classification, ranges from hot and dry to very hot and very dry, showing annual mean precipitation approaching 200 mm [14]. Extensive grazing is practiced in the area.

FIGURE 5. Map of El Rosario, Baja California Sur showing the place (*) where specimens were collected and recorded

Discussion

Spectrograms were generated using the software Adobe Audition® version 3.0 to analyse the echolocation signals. The signals were recorded using a time expansion system; consequently, they have been shifted to the sonic range using a factor of 10. The original axes have been preserved.

Figure 6 shows conventional field recordings. In these recordings the detector is pointed to the area in which it is more likely to observe a bat. In Figure 6.1 the signal from a bat flying over the detector has been registered (1). The signal in the lower portion of the spectrogram, having strong energy components around 15 kHz (2), is the noise produced by the mist net. Although this noise comes from a different band of frequencies, some components go up to 50 kHz interfering with the signals from the bat, so no conventional low pass filter will suffice.

Using a time expansion system shifts ultrasound signals to the audible range, but as a side effect, it also shifts audible signals to lower ranges and makes them last longer. Some otherwise known common signals are therefore difficult to identify and to eliminate. This is the case of bat wing movements, perching sounds, and other sounds generated by the bat in the sonic range. Anthropogenic sounds, such as walking and breathing, and some natural sounds have also frequency components in the ultrasound region, which might interfere with the echolocation signal recordings.

Figure 6.2 shows a signal recorded from a bat (1), a strong sound interference (2) from walking on rocks, and net handling. In the first portion of the signal (1) the sound of the net (2) overlaps the signal of the bat. There is a second and a third portion of the bat's echolocation signal, and although the signal is not masked by the sound produced by the net, the dynamic range of the recording has been reduced due to the noise, and consequently, the bat's signal looks weaker.

On contrast, Figure 7 shows echolocation signals from three species recorded inside the chamber. There are some evident advantages clearly seen. The chamber reduces the possibility of recording a second individual, such as in Figure 1. Gender, species and behaviour of the bat recorded are known, whilst on a free flying bat this cannot be known for sure. Other sources of noise, either from conspecifics or insects are excluded from the recordings. Even anthropogenic sounds can be better controlled. The effects that wind and temperature gradients have on the recordings are also diminished. Pulse repetition rate on field recording have been associated consistently to specific vegetation structure [15]. Since the vegetation structure depends on temporal and geographical conditions, the use of a chamber makes it possible to compare signals excluding this factor.

Figure 8 shows a portion of the recorded signals for *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus* (a), *Lasiurus xanthinus* (b), and *Leptonycteris yerbabuena* (c) shown in Figure 7. Single chirps recorded in the portable chamber are presented for comparison. The characteristic pulses (I) in the three species can be clearly identified. The lowest frequencies for the pulses are: 41 kHz, 27 kHz, and 38 kHz, and the peak frequencies are 48 kHz, 35 kHz, and 63 kHz, respectively. Using only these two parameters, it is possible to distinguish species.

FIGURE 6. Field recording spectrograms. Notice the presence of noise in middle and low frequencies and the low signal to noise ratio. Echolocation signals (1), noise from rocks, nets (2). Spectrogram setting: 1024 point FFT, Hamming window, 50% overlap.

FIGURE 7. Spectrograms of echolocation signals from *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus* (a), *Lasiurus xanthinus* (b), and *Leptonycteris yerbabuena* (c) recorded in the portable chamber. Notice the signal to noise ratio. Spectrogram setting: 2048 point FFT, Hamming window, 50% overlap.

FIGURE 8. Spectrograms chirp signals from *Parastrellus hesperus hesperus* (a), *Lasiurus xanthinus* (b), and *Leptonycteris yerbabuena* (c) recorded in the portable chamber. Spectrogram setting: 512 point FFT, Hamming window, 50% overlap.

CONCLUSIONS

The variability among echolocation signals recorded has led to studies focused on the use of different bat detectors for field recordings, but no studies have been directed to control recording conditions. Since the signals produced by the bat depend on environmental conditions, biotic factors and navigation strategies controlling these factors might contribute to obtain consistent and comparable recordings. The chamber proposed not only helps from an acoustic point of view, but also helps to control these variables having a positive effect on the recordings.

There are important advantages of using these controlled conditions. The effect of external sounds, wind, and temperature gradients is reduced allowing clear recordings with good signal to noise ratios, which facilitate to characterize the species signal. Another advantage is that having the individual with known species, sex, and possible age, facilitates the creation of a reliable and comparable catalogue of echolocation signals. Besides, inside the chamber the bat's behaviour during sound production is limited to a few conducts, and the signals produced are not influenced by vegetation structure.

The portable chamber presented here can be constructed using readily available materials. Although its performance for bat recording was demonstrated, it could be used in studies of other species producing sound on high frequency range.

FUTURE WORK

The use of a portable anechoic chamber has advantages for species identification, a fundamental prerequisite for successful ecological research and conservation. Identification protocols (call libraries) for bat species from arid habitat recorded under controlled conditions will be created.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We express appreciation to Julio Manuel Hernández Gutiérrez, Carlos David Valenzuela, Mayra de la Paz Cuevas for their aid in the field test, and Sergio Ticul Álvarez-Castañeda for his help in taxonomic identification. Diana Dorantes of CIBNOR provided useful editorial suggestions. Gerardo García for his help on map edition. This Project was undertaken with a grant provided by Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad (CONABIO) [GT033 "Inventario de los murciélagos de las zonas desérticas y semidesérticas del

norte de México” to Patricia Cortés-Calva]. Scientific collection licenses were granted by SEMARNAT (FAUT-0051).

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